

Together,
there's
something
science
can do.

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[Revisto](#), an AI company focused on pharmaceutical marketing compliance, announced on November 18, 2024 that it has secured \$4 million in seed funding led by LiveOak Ventures, with participation from Eli Lilly and Company, Tau Ventures, and Arkin Digital Health, bringing their total funding to \$6 million. The company's says that its AI technology tackles the medical, legal, and regulatory (MLR) review process for pharmaceutical marketing materials by leveraging terabytes of proprietary data and real-time FDA regulations to automate traditionally manual workflows.

On November 12, 2024, [researchers at the Neuro announced they have received \\$1.5M from Quebec's CQDM to develop YCharOS](#), an innovative platform that independently validates commercial antibodies used in laboratory research - addressing a critical issue where at least 50% of antibodies in the \$2-3B global market fail to perform as claimed. Led by neuroscientists Peter McPherson and Carl Laflamme, YCharOS performs comparative analyses of antibodies targeting the same proteins and publishes results in an open-access format, aiming to improve research reproducibility and accelerate neurological disease treatment development while strengthening Quebec's research ecosystem.

[Canada's Dental Care Plan \(CDCP\) has now provided care to over 1 million Canadians](#), with 2.7 million approved for coverage, saving participants an average of \$730 on dental services. Starting November 2024, the program is expanding to include preauthorized services like partial dentures and crowns, while also accepting paper claims alongside electronic submissions, with 89% of the country's active oral health providers (over 22,340) now participating in the program.

[UNESCO and CODATA have launched a global consultation project](#) called Data Policy for Times of Crisis (DPTC) to develop guidance on data sharing during crises, building on lessons from COVID-19 and other recent emergencies through the lens of open science principles. The initiative, announced October 21, 2024, aims to create practical resources including a factsheet, guidance document, and policy checklist to help policymakers and scientists design efficient data-sharing policies that address both immediate crisis response and long-term recovery needs.